

FORMATION OF A DATABASE OF LUNG DISEASE SOUND SIGNALS

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Abstract. *This work is focused on the formation of a database of lung disease sound signals. The main stages and tasks of collecting, recording, processing, and classifying sound signals are presented. Methods of processing and analyzing sound signals based on neural networks provide the capabilities to obtain acceptable databases for automating disease diagnostics, making them more reliable compared to human knowledge.*

Keywords: *lung diseases, sound signals, databases, collection, recording, processing, classification, methods, algorithms.*

Introduction

The organization of disease prevention and diagnosis processes in medicine requires high accuracy and speed. Currently, the advent of new methods and approaches based on modern information technologies offers further advancements in this area. Neural networks and particularly deep learning technologies open new possibilities for diagnosing and predicting diseases in medicine. Methods of automatic analysis implemented by neural networks allow diseases to be diagnosed with much greater accuracy and reliability than human reasoning. Thus, the use of neural networks allows the automation of diagnostic processes, making them more reliable compared to human reasoning.

Currently, lung diseases hold one of the leading positions in the statistics of work capacity losses in all countries globally (especially those with developed industries). Hence, the relevance of research in this field is undeniable, and work in this direction evolves with the development of information and computer technology tools, new-generation sensors, artificial intelligence methods in diagnostics and decision-making, and telemedicine tools.

Lung diseases can cause various health issues for humans, and their early detection, diagnosis, and treatment are crucial. The method of detecting lung diseases through sound signals must be implemented using high-precision models capable of detecting sound noises that are difficult for humans to hear or sense [1-5].

Sound noises are a unique indicator characterizing the functioning of the lungs and the body's overall state, as they are not only due to the mechanical work of the lungs aimed at ensuring the necessary concentration of gases in the body but also depend on a number of both external and internal factors. Lung diseases cause pathological changes throughout the body, so their timely diagnosis during screening using simple ("household") methods in mass examinations is intended to improve the quality of medical care for the prevention and timely treatment of socially significant diseases.

Methods of processing and analyzing sound signals based on neural networks provide the possibilities to obtain acceptable results and automate diagnostic processes, making them more reliable compared to human knowledge. This requires the creation of a database of sound signals [6].

Hence, the goal of the research was to study the practical means, methods, and techniques, and the mathematical tools for forming, analyzing, and processing a database of sound signals for the subsequent diagnosis of lung conditions.

Materials and Methods of Research

Prerequisites for the Formation, Analysis, and Processing of the Sound Signal Database

The study of methods for collecting and forming a database of sound signals using neural networks, along with their analysis and processing, is a crucial factor for the accurate diagnosis of lung diseases. An essential factor is the formation of the necessary sound signals and their inclusion in the final database for proper and precise diagnosis.

There exist scientific studies on the significance of sound signals in diagnosing lung diseases [1-5]. During traditional auscultation, doctors listen to a patient's breathing sounds through a stethoscope and attempt to identify various diseases. The skill and experience of doctors in detecting diseases through sound signals is an important aspect of the diagnostic process. However, automated methods for detecting and analyzing sound signals can greatly assist doctors [1]. Specifically, neural networks and deep learning technologies are effective in identifying lung diseases by analyzing breathing sounds (Fig. 1) [2]. With deep learning algorithms, it is possible to accurately analyze sounds that are hard to hear or unsuitable for humans, aiding in the more accurate diagnosis of lung diseases [3].

Fig-1. Deep Learning Technologies.

Results from previous studies show many achievements and approaches in this field, but they have some limitations [4]. For instance, many studies were conducted based on a limited database, which makes it difficult to generalize the results. Additionally, different methods of evaluating lung sound signals were used, making it challenging to compare results [5]. For example, some databases lack sufficient data on certain types of diseases or have insufficient data diversity [6]. To overcome these limitations, it is necessary to expand the database and apply uniform evaluation methods.

Currently, there are several globally recognized and widely used databases that are a valuable resource for researchers and doctors. Therefore, the existing databases are of particular importance, and their advantages and limitations are analyzed as follows:

PhysioNet is an internationally recognized medical database that contains various physiological signals and their indicators. This platform has a particularly comprehensive dataset of lung sound signals. PhysioNet lists patients' breathing sounds, pulse rate, and other important physiological parameters [7]. Its main advantage is that its data is recognized and reliable in everything.

The i2b2 (Informatics for Integrating Biology & the Bedside) database was created to integrate big data in medicine and biology. The platform contains comprehensive and diverse data, including patient sound signals and medical records. The i2b2 platform is convenient for research and distinguished by the completeness of its data [8]. Using this database, researchers can analyze data and conduct new scientific studies.

The Respiratory Sound Database (RSD) is a specialized database designed for recording and analyzing lung sound signals. The main advantage of RSD is the availability of high-quality recordings of patients' breathing sounds. Thanks to this database, it is possible to create neural network-based diagnostic systems for studying sound signals and identifying lung diseases [9]. The RSD platform is a valuable resource for researchers, allowing them to identify lung diseases. When selecting or developing a database, special attention should be paid to their advantages, namely: complete and high-quality data, internationally recognized, and user-friendly interfaces for researchers. The information obtained through databases plays a crucial role in creating and training new neural network models. Researchers and doctors can use these resources to improve and enhance the diagnostic process.

Thus, when forming a database for diagnosing lung diseases based on sound signals, effective utilization of available resources is essential. Additionally, it is important to form databases in accordance with the local nature and ecological indicators of specific regions worldwide. This is the main factor in diagnosing diseases.

Formation of a Sound Signal Database

The use of neural networks for diagnosing lung diseases allows for the development of a comprehensive and high-quality database of sound signals [1]. Therefore, the most modern methods of sound signal recognition are necessary. Mathematical methods such as correlation analysis, fast Fourier transform, fuzzy logic, and probabilistic methods were analyzed and used for recognizing and counting sound signals. Great importance is placed on forming a lung disease database consisting of stages: collection, recording, processing, and classification of sound signals. Each stage requires a serious approach for accurate and high-quality diagnosis.

Collection of Sound Signals

The process of collecting sound signals for diagnosing lung diseases is of great significance. For diagnosing sound signals based on neural networks, the accuracy and quality of the data are crucial. The process of collecting sound signals is carried out through clinical studies, conducted in collaboration with doctors and patients.

The collection of sound signals is based on clinical studies and special protocols. During clinical studies, patients' breathing sounds are recorded in clinical settings. Special clinical research protocols are developed and strictly followed [10, 11]. These protocols ensure high quality and reproducibility of sound signals at each stage. Studies are usually conducted in hospitals and medical centers with the participation of doctors and researchers.

Recording of Sound Signals

During this process, patients' breathing sounds are recorded using high-quality stethoscopes and microphones. Patients' breathing sounds are recorded in clinical settings, and during this process, doctors and researchers must consider patient's comfort. Recorded sound signals determine the accuracy and reliability of the diagnostic system's performance. Therefore, it is necessary to follow high standards and methodologies in the recording process [1, 2]. It is important to capture patient's breathing in various positions (e.g., normal breathing, deep breathing, snoring, etc.), which ensures accurate classification of diseases (Fig. 2). Therefore, it is crucial to use high standards and methodologies when recording sound signals.

Fig. 2. Types of Sound Signals

Processing of Sound Signals

The process of sound signal processing includes several stages to adapt the recorded signals to the requirements of cleanliness and quality. These steps involve filtering, separation, and segmentation of the signals.

In the filtering stage, the signal is cleared of background noises and the main sound components are highlighted [12-16]. The process of filtering sound signals is an important stage in enhancing the quality and accuracy of the recorded signals, which allows making an accurate diagnosis for the patient. During filtering, effective extraction of redundant and unnecessary information from the recorded sound signals is achieved. This stage involves clearing the signal of background noises and highlighting the main sound components [3].

Lung noises such as breath sounds (*murmura respiratoria*) arise due to the act of breathing. Distinctions are made between primary and additional, or incidental, breath sounds. Issues related to lung auscultation are extensively discussed in the work [17], which includes descriptions of both normal and pathological primary breath sounds.

Analysis of existing collections of breath sounds (BS) shows that they vary by key recording parameters: quantization frequency by level and time, duration, processing methodologies, and storage formats.

This stage employs various filters: low-pass filters, high-pass filters, band-pass filters, and notch filters. With these filters, high-precision algorithms can be developed to obtain useful sounds influenced by background noise, patient movement, and other external factors [5]. The noise filtering process requires effective extraction of redundant and unnecessary information from the recorded sound signals. Methods such as spectral filtering, mean-square filtering, and spectral analysis methods are used to reduce noise [18]. These methods eliminate background noise in the sound signals and distinctly highlight the primary diagnostic signals. It is crucial to preserve the integral parts of the main sound signal during this process.

Separation and analysis of the main signal components are important for diagnosis. In the process of separating the main parts of the sound signal, it becomes possible to highlight the sound segments necessary for diagnosis. Various signal processing methods are used in this process, such as time series analysis, spectral analysis, wavelet transformations, Fourier transform [2]. These methods highlight and analyze important parts of the sound signal. Through spectral analysis, the signals are used to detect various manifestations of diseases [18]. During segmentation, diagnostic indicators are determined in each tested segment, and these segments are fed into the neural network-based model.

Classification of Sound Signals

At this stage, the obtained useful sound signals are classified by diseases. Neural networks and machine learning methods such as K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN), decision trees, and Support Vector Machines (SVM) are used to identify the components and characteristics of the sound signal [19]. With these methods, sound signals are grouped and classified by types of diseases and symptoms. Neural networks analyze this data and classify it according to different diseases. The signals are classified into groups based on diseases, and a model is trained for diagnosis based on clinical analysis [6]. The accuracy of the classification process determines the effectiveness of the diagnostic system.

The classified sound signals are used to train the neural network model. This process employs deep learning algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). A complex dataset is used to create high-precision classifiers [20].

The high accuracy of filtering and classification processes is an important factor in creating a valuable and reliable database. It ensures the reliability of diagnostic processes and increases the accuracy of disease detection.

The sound signals generated by the database are analyzed, and the diagnostic results are verified for compliance with specified standards. During testing, parameters such as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and the performance of the neural network model are evaluated [21].

With the complete and accurate execution of all the above steps, a high-quality and extensive database for diagnosing lung diseases based on sound signals is formed. This makes neural network-based diagnostic systems more reliable and efficient.

Conclusions

A lung disease database is one of the main components of medical diagnostic systems. For the use of neural networks based on diagnostic methods that rely on sound signals to detect lung diseases, it is necessary to form a comprehensive and high-quality database.

Methods for forming, analyzing, and processing primary sound signals based on neural networks are crucial for obtaining useful, high-quality, and specific sound signals. These methods

play a significant role in improving diagnostic processes and enhancing patient health in modern medicine.

The generated database is used to train various diagnostic methods and neural network models. The broader and higher the quality of this database is, the more effective and accurate the model will be. It is necessary to constantly update and expand the database to ensure the continuous development and improvement of the diagnostic system.

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